

DAMAGE CHARACTERISATION IN CFRP USING ACOUSTIC EMISSION, X-RAY TOMOGRAPHY AND FBG SENSORS

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SUMMARY

Composite materials are susceptible to low energy impact damage and hence it is important that such damage can be detected, quantified and understood. This research assessed the ability of fiber Bragg gratings (FBG) embedded within a carbon fibre laminate to detect damage occurring from a low velocity impact. It also considered whether the FBGs are able to characterise the damage within the material.

A clear link was made between the amount of residual strain experienced by the FBG and the amount of damage occurring within the carbon fibre by use of X-ray computed tomography to view the internal damage. It was shown that FBGs embedded parallel to the carbon fibre direction are able to characterise fibre fracture whilst FBGs embedded perpendicularly are able to characterise micro cracking and matrix cracking.

The acoustic emissions (AE) from the carbon fibre during impact testing and images the computed tomography were also used to characterise the damage mechanisms acting during the impact tests and compared with the with the strain response of the FBG. It was demonstrated that the speed of the strain response gave an indication of the damage mechanisms acting within the fibre, with high speed responses correlating with fibre fracture and gross matrix cracking

Keywords: CFRP, impact damage, acoustic emission, FBG, x-ray tomography

INTRODUCTION

Impact damage mechanisms and methods of detecting impact damage of composite have both been extensively researched for many years. Depending on the energy of impact, the composite architecture and quality, the damage which occurs under a low energy impact may comprise a combination of matrix cracking, fibre fracture, fibre buckling and delaminations. The early stages of a typical carbon fibre structural composite are characterised by matrix damage whereas delaminations and fibre fracture are more typical of higher energy impact [1].

With regard to detecting damage, ultrasonics, radiography, fibre-optic sensors, acoustic emission (AE), X-ray tomography (micro CT scan) and destructive microscopy all have advantages and disadvantages. The issues involved in the selection of the detection method involve ease of use, cost, damage resolution and not least the objectives of the detection. For example ultrasonics and radiography require the part to be taken out of

service whilst AE and FBGs can provide in-situ detection but do not give a direct measure of damage or identification of the damage mechanism.

FBGs which when embedded in a composite laminate can provide in-situ measurements of strain. The problem is that strain measurements which are not a direct measure of condition or damage. The FBG field has been fast moving and in many senses can be regarded as being mature. For a comprehensive review of the application of conventional optical fibres and fibre Bragg gratings in advanced composite structures including impact damage detection, the reader is referred to the review paper by Kuang and Cantrell [2]

Much of the work involving fibre optic sensors has concentrated on detecting the impact event rather than the consequences. Tsutsui et al [3,4] have used fibre optic sensors and FBGs to detect impact damage initiation and location in composite laminates and stiffened panels and Kuang et al [5] demonstrated the potential for FBGs to detect an impact event and monitor the progression of damage in fibre metal laminates. Recently, Tsuda [6] demonstrated the feasibility of a damage monitoring system based on the intensity of modulation of light reflected from fibre Bragg grating sensors.

Whilst it has been clearly demonstrated that it is possible to detect low energy impacts by the recording of a dynamic or residual strain, the recorded values cannot be easily correlated with actual damage and the damage mechanism. The strain values are dependent on a host of (non-material) factors including the location of the sensor with respect to the impact, the geometry of the testpiece (thickness), the impactor geometry and the properties and construction of the composite laminate. Not surprisingly, this makes the impact process difficult to model. Any meaningful model requires the input of relevant properties and this may explain Kuang and Cantrell's [2] observation that there is very little literature concerning the use of FBG sensors for impact damage mechanism detection in composite materials.

Acoustic emission (AE) testing relies on the understanding that, when damage occurs in a component/specimen, there is a sudden redistribution of stress within the system. This then causes a generation of transient elastic waves which then propagate through the material. In AE testing these elastic waves can be detected and converted to electrical waves which can subsequently be analysed in order to gain information regarding the source of the waves and, hence, the point of damage within a material. It has been reported that AE testing is not only limited to determining the onset of damage, but can also be used to obtain additional information on the damage mechanisms present during testing [7].

To observe damage within the specimens non-destructively, high resolution X-ray computed tomography (CT) scanning is a valuable technique. CT scanning creates a three-dimensional (3-D) image of an object. It is generally regarded that CT is a useful technique for investigating impact-damaged CFRP because it reveals the distribution of delaminations and matrix cracks without the need for physical sectioning. Schilling P.J. et. al. investigated the ability of CT scanning to characterise the type, geometry and orientation of defects within a specimen [8]. The tests were undertaken using a micro-CT scanner similar to that available for use in this research. Based on scanning electron microscopy, cracks of 0.5 – 1 μm . were identified. In addition delaminations and microcracking were also identified.

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

The aims and objectives of this work were to evaluate the potential of embedded fibre Bragg grating sensors and acoustic emission sensors for quantifying damage and identifying damage mechanisms in unidirectional carbon fibre epoxy resin composite subjected to cumulative impacts. To this end the results from these sensors are interpreted in the light of CT scan and microscopic analysis on sections taken through impact damaged regions.

EXPERIMENTAL METHOD

Materials for impact testing

Test pieces produced for impact testing specimens were 100x100mm 6-ply unidirectional carbon fiber laminates manufactured from WE91 prepreg, 600g weight (Gurit).

Optical fibers, containing a FBG were accurately embedded both in the fiber direction and also in the transverse direction (perpendicular to the fibers) allowing all types of damage to be detected by the FBGs. The fibers were embedded between the 3rd and 4th (middle) layers of the specimen in order to provide protection for the fibres on impact. By placing the gratings in this position, lower measured residual strains were accepted.

The laminates were cured using an oven cure cycle with a ramp rate of 3°C/min and a cure of 1 hour at 120°C. This resulted in a composite with a void content between 2 & 4%.

Impact testing

The low velocity impact tests were carried out using a drop weight impact test rig (Figure.1). This test rig holds the 100x100mm specimens by clamping the four edges securely between two flat rectangular frames and a circular test window to allow the specimen to flex under impact. The impactor itself is a hemispherical nose which was dropped from 3 different heights to give different impact energies. The rig also featured a spring-back mechanism which prevented the impactor from impacting the specimen multiple times.

The impact energies used were 3, 5 and 8 joules corresponding to drop heights of 0.46, 0.77 and 1.23m respectively. The initial impact was 3J and during which FBG and acoustic emission sensor readings were obtained. The specimen was then removed from the impact rig and CT scanned prior to being accurately replaced in the impact rig and the process repeated for 5 and 8 J impacts.

Figure 1 Impact drop tower

Sensors

The test was set up such that the impact was approximately 10mm equidistant from each of the gratings. The FBGs were interrogated using a Fiber Bragg grating swept laser interrogator supplied by Micron Optics. The wavelength shift was then interpreted using LabVIEW™, the standard software provided with the interrogator.

The Fiber Bragg grating interrogation system returned a wavelength throughout the experiment. However, the interest was in the strain experienced by the FBG. In order to calculate this, the following formula was used:

$$\Delta\varepsilon = \frac{\Delta\lambda}{0.78\lambda}$$

Where ε is the strain in μ strains, λ is the initial wavelength of the FBG and $\Delta\lambda$ is the change in wavelength.

During the impact, some of the energy may be dissipated as heat, such a heat fluctuation may cause a wavelength shift in the FBG as they are extremely sensitive to thermal variations [9] which could then be mistaken for a residual strain. For this reason, the specimen was left to cool until after impact until the wavelength had stabilised.

In order to detect the acoustic emission from the sensor during the impact test, four AE sensors were glued to the specimen in the rig. These were positioned equidistant from the expected site of impact using the zonal location technique allowing the AE responses to be traced to a particular point within the specimen.

Damage assessment

The damage of the specimens was assessed predominantly by CT scans and microscopy. The CT scans were obtained using a X-Tek 160Xi CT scan. Several specimens of the same carbon fiber material were stacked together so the x-ray penetration would be even during the rotation of the specimen. The area of the specimen scanned focused primarily on the area directly adjacent to the centre of impact and the

fiber in order to gain a higher resolution of this area. The CT scans were then reconstructed and viewed using VG Studiomax.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Description of Damage

The 3 Joule impact caused a matrix crack to propagate from the position of maximum tensile stress on the lower face of the specimen (directly beneath the impact site) to approximately the midplane position (Figure 2)

Figure 2 – 3J impact

The 5 Joule impact produced a much higher level of damage with the beginning of some shear cone damage and fibre breakage occurring. Figure 3 shows both the tensile crack on the underside of the specimen, detected after the 3 Joule impact, and a new crack propagating from the top surface of the specimen. Such a crack develops due to the shear forces developed by the impact and hence the failure mode is known as the shear cone failure.

Figure 3- 5J impact

The 8 Joule impact extended the damage initiated by the lower energy impacts. Figure 4a shows that both the shear cone crack and the tensile crack have grown beyond the size of those detected after the previous impact tests. There has also been further fibre cracking around the site of the previous crack causing it to enlarge. It can also be seen that the crack is now coupled with a delamination, further delaminations and a point where the tensile crack has propagated throughout the whole specimen are seen in Figure 4b.

Figure 4a – 8J impact showing extended tensile crack and shear cone cracks

Figure 4 b - 8J impact showing crack and delamination

It should be noted that the resolution (30 μm) was not sufficient to identify matrix microcracking.

FBG -Effect of Fibre Direction

FBG traces for the 3J impact are shown in Figure 5. It can be seen that the strain parallel to the fibres is small and compressive whereas that perpendicular to the fibres is tensile and a decade larger.

Figure 5a –perpendicular FBG -3J impact

Figure 5b – parallel FBG - 3J impact

With the fibres embedded between the 3rd and 4th layers of a 6 ply laminate, it was not expected that either fibre would experience any compression. However, it would appear that, during curing. The fibre parallel to the carbon fibre direction moved upward within the composite, the position of the optical fibres can be easily seen in the CT scans, and an image depicting the point of fibre placement can be seen in Figure 6

Figure 6

The actual strains experienced by the two fibres also vary substantially, with the perpendicular fibre experiencing strains an order of magnitude larger than the parallel fibre. This result can be attributed to the strain in the perpendicular direction being a matrix dominated property, with strain in the parallel direction being a fibre dominated property with the fibres being significantly stronger than the matrix [10].

There is also variation in the speed at which the maximum strain is achieved between the parallel and perpendicular fibres, with the perpendicular fibre having a much faster response with no data points occurring between the minimum and maximum points of strain indicating that this strain was achieved in less than 0.01s. This rapid strain rate indicates that there was a catastrophic failure mode at work, such as a fibre break, whilst a slower strain rate indicates a more gradual process such as matrix crack propagation.

Effect of Impact Energy on residual strain

The effect of impact energy on residual strain is shown in Figure 7. It can be seen that the perpendicular residual strain increases with impact energy. This is consistent with the damage observed in the CT scans and the research of Takeda [11]. The axial compressive strain also increased but by a much smaller amount.

Figure 7 – effect of impact energy on residual strain

Acoustic Emission -Effect of Impact Energy

In order to analyse the data, the events recorded by the AE sensors were plotted on a graph of energy against time (the energy of the impact itself has been excluded because it was significantly greater than the events associated with damage events of interest in this research). The response for the 3 Joule impact is given in Figure 8.

Events with energy above 100 eU are generally considered significant with regard to damage. At 3J the maximum energy was 300 eU. This is consistent with the tensile cracking damage observed in the CT scans. To enable full analysis of this event, the other properties recorded must be examined. These are shown in Table 1 which also includes the properties of the 5J impacts. The results of the 8J impact are not included because it is believed they were affected by saturation of the AE sensors and hence not representative of the impact event.

Property	3J	5J
Amplitude	79.1 dB	87.4
Rise Time	1317 μ s	257
Duration	1900 μ s	2441
Energy	294 eU	1040

Table 1

The most significant of these properties is the high amplitude value of 79.1 dB. This is also consistent with a very damaging event. The rise time and duration also allow the response to be characterised. A long duration again indicates a damaging event and the rise time/duration ratio details the speed at which energy is released [12]. Here the ratio of rise time to duration is high indicating a slow release of energy.

The nature of a specific event can also be characterised by the frequency distribution of its transient response. Highly damaging events have also been found to have a peak in frequencies detected between 600 and 700 kHz. However, these frequencies are not often detected due to attenuation by the material [13]. This implies that in order for a signal of such frequency to be detected, it must have been extremely strong initially.

The results from the 5J impact were analysed in a similar manner and are shown in Figure 9. The increase in energy to 5 Joules resulted in a substantial increase in the energy of the most significant event detected by the AE sensors, an increase in the duration and reduction in the rise time. The amplitude was only marginally increased (Table 1).

As a result in the reduction in the rise time and increase of the duration, the rise time/duration ratio is significantly lower than that experienced in the 3 Joule impact. This faster release of energy is indicative of a faster failure mechanism, such as fibre breakage, whereas the slower release experienced by the 3 Joule impact would tend to indicate a slower mechanism such a matrix cracking. This is consistent with the evidence from the CT scans which showed shear cone cracking, compressive fibre

fractures and delaminations at 5 and 8 Joule impacts but only a tensile rear face matrix crack at 3J

Figure 8 AE energy and frequency response for 3J impact

Figure 9 AE response for 5J impact

The frequency distributions of the transient responses from the AE response from the 5 Joule impact also showed a peak between 600 and 700 kHz. In the 5 Joule test, the highest energy event was not the only acoustic event to display high amplitude and short rise time/duration ratios, with transient responses revealing that the 200 eU and 150 eU events also displayed peaks between 600 and 700 kHz.

SUMMATIVE DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

The FBG results above indicated that there was an increasing resultant strain with increasing impact energy, this result was consistent with the results from the acoustic emission testing and the CT scans. A simple consideration of all of these results separately and independently gives little measure of actual damage or the damage mechanisms occurring. However, consideration of all of these results in combination allows such analysis.

With respect to the fibre embedded perpendicular to the carbon fibre direction, and in the direction governed by the matrix properties, significant strains were seen at each of the impact energy. The CT results indicate that the damage in this direction was predominantly due to matrix cracking and with the microscopy it can also be seen that there was micro cracking occurring. The AE results from the 3 Joule impact also indicate that matrix cracking is the predominant damage mechanism since only the perpendicular fibre displaying any significant strain at this point. CT results also indicate increasing damage with increasing impact energy which correlates with the increasing strain experienced by the perpendicular fibre.

The results obtained from the FBG embedded parallel to the carbon fibre direction also yielded some important results. It was shown that strain in the carbon fibre direction increased with increasing impact energy, to the point where the optical fibre containing the FBG fractured in the third test. This agreed with the CT and AE results which did not show any evidence of fibre fracture at lower energy but suggested the predominant damage mechanism to be matrix cracking. However these results did suggest that fracturing failure mechanisms were acting in the higher energy tests.

It can also be seen that the speed of the strain response of the FBG is an important parameter in the characterisation of energy; this is comparable with the rise time/duration parameter discussed regarding the acoustic emissions. The speed of the strain response can be seen to be faster where higher energy damage mechanisms are known to take place, with the speed of response in the parallel fibre due to fibre fracture being under 0.01 seconds. A rapid response was also seen in the highest energy impact energy producing an equally fast strain response in the perpendicular fibre, this characterises widespread damage due to the propagation of multiple matrix cracks.

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